

Study of pigment potential of *Micrococcus luteus*, isolated from *Fenneropenaeus indicus* a local Indian Prawn Sp.

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ABSTRACT

The marine biosphere ecology has not been fully studied for possible secondary metabolite sources. Marine crustaceans are a relatively unknown source of critical biological metabolites. The primary goal of this work was to isolate pigmented bacteria that produce L-asparaginase from a native Prawn sp. (*Fenneropenaeus indicus*). Nine pigmented L-asparaginase producing isolates were chosen for further study from the 93 screened isolates. KP07, a high L-asparaginase producing isolate, was chosen for further investigation into its pigment potential. Phylogenetic analysis revealed that the isolate KP07 was 99.72% similar to *Micrococcus luteus* NCTC 2665(T). Methanol was used as a solvent to extract the yellow pigment. The antioxidant activity of the pigment was detected as radical scavenging activity with a maximum percent RSA of 66.31% at 40 ug/ml using the DPPH assay. Agar well diffusion testing indicated that the pigment was very harmful to both gram-positive and gram-negative bacteria. The presence of Octadecanoic acid, which has important industrial and medical applications, was studied by GC-MS analysis.

Keywords: Prawns, *Fenneropenaeus indicus*, *Micrococcus luteus*, Marine Crustaceans, Octadecanoic acid

INTRODUCTION

Marine crustaceans, like prawns, are keystone species that regulate populations of smaller organisms and contribute to the cycling of nutrients in oceanic ecosystems. They are an essential part of many species' diets²³. Due to its distinct features, such as the genetic makeup and environments of marine microorganisms, the marine environment differs from the terrestrial environment³⁵. This resulted in the identification of numerous enzymes from marine bacteria, actinomycetes, fungi, and other microorganisms that had unique properties. These enzymes are now used in sectors like pharmaceuticals, food additives, and fine chemicals⁴⁴. The common name for the *Fenneropenaeus indicus* species is the Indian prawn or banana prawn. Prawns are known by their scientific name, *Dendrobranchiata*, and are categorized as belonging to the phylum arthropoda's decapod suborder. They are widely dispersed throughout the tropical and subtropical waters of the Indian and western Pacific Oceans and are highly valuable economically in terms of foreign exchange²⁹. They are typically reared in ponds and tanks using a combination of artificial and natural feeds. Several health advantages and a good source of nutrition can be found in prawns. They are a good source of protein, fat, minerals such as zinc, iron, and selenium, vitamins such as vitamin D and vitamin B₁₂, and omega-3 fatty acids. Prawns, a type of marine crustacean, have a variety of uses. In biomedical research, they are used to study the effects of pollution, disease, and other environmental factors on aquatic organisms. They serve as an indicator of aquatic ecosystem health. Certain prawn pigments such as astaxanthin, lutein, zeaxanthin, crustacyanin⁶, canthaxanthin, echinenone¹² and beta-carotene⁴⁵ are being researched for potential use in pharmaceuticals, particularly for their anti-inflammatory and antioxidant properties. Furthermore, some prawn-derived compounds, particularly exfoliants, are used in cosmetics³. There is relatively less literature available on the characterization, diversity, and potential applications of pigmented bacteria in prawns, which makes it an area with a lot of potential for exploration for research and commercial industry.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Sample Collection:

Indian prawn samples, or *Fenneropenaeus indicus*, were obtained from Kopri Fish Market in Thane, Maharashtra (19° 11' 2.6556" N, 72° 58' 21.2304" E). To avoid deterioration during transportation, they were placed in a styrofoam box with ice packs. Until processing, they were stored at 4°C in a refrigerator in an airtight plastic container. At Vasai, Maharashtra, India (19° 20' 45.4488" N, 72° 47' 9.8484" E), seawater was collected in five liters from the epipelagic zone. Utilizing Whatman No. 1 filter paper, water was purified and kept at room temperature for media preparation.

Primary Screening of Pigmented Bacteria:

The samples were aseptically thoroughly cleaned with distilled water. Following cleaning with 70% ethanol, the sample was placed in storage for isolation. The prawn's gut was deveined, blended with a mortar and pestle, and centrifuged for 10 minutes at 4°C at 10,000 rpm. The pellet was discarded, but the supernatant was kept for isolation. The supernatant was used to prepare for upcoming isolation techniques. The isolated prawn gut supernatant was streaked onto Horikoshi, Nutrient, and Starch Casein Agar. Horikoshi and Starch Casein Agar media were incubated for 7 days, while the nutrient agar was incubated at room temperature for 24 to 48 hours. All media were supplemented with 25 to 40 mM Nalidixic acid to prevent the growth of Gram-negative bacteria. All the primary screened yellow pigmented isolates were preserved at refrigeration temperature on sterile Nutrient Agar slants¹¹.

Secondary Screening:

Out of nine yellow pigmented isolates only one isolate labelled as KP07 was found to produce more L-asparaginase as compared to others. Therefore isolate KP07 was taken for further study with respect to pigment extraction and studying its antibacterial and anti-oxidant activity (**Further study of L-asparaginase from isolate KP07 is not the part of this article**).

Identification Of Bacterial Isolate:

In order to identify the bacterial isolate at the molecular level⁸, the 16S rRNA gene was partially sequenced. In order to achieve this, the genomic DNA of the bacterial strains was extracted using the common Phenol-Chloroform-Isomayl alcohol (PCI) extraction protocol. After that, the 16S rRNA gene was extracted from the genomic DNA, which was then amplified using a hot-start PCR²⁸. This was accomplished using the primers 16F27 [5'-CCA GAG TTT GAT CMT GGC TCA G-3'] and 16R1492 [5'-TAC GGY TAC CTT GTT ACG ACT T-3']. The amplification procedure was carried out in a thermocycler and included 35 cycles of denaturation at 94°C for 45 seconds, annealing at 56°C for 45 seconds, and extension at 72°C for a minute. The denaturation step was carried out at 95°C for a minute. A 5-minute final extension at 72°C was also performed³⁴. On Agarose gel electrophoresis, the amplified 16S rRNA gene PCR product was examined. It was then purified using PEG-NaCl precipitation, and the sequence was cycled using a primer. On an ABI® 3730XL automated DNA sequencing machine, each position was read at least twice³². Additional internal primers were used to sequence from both ends for this²⁵.

Phylogenetic Tree:

A phylogenetic tree is a graphical representation of the evolutionary relationships among taxa or species. It is constructed using molecular or morphological data, examined using mathematical and computational techniques to infer evolutionary relationships, and utilized to look into the evolution of traits, the timing of events, and the origins of populations. The phylogenetic history was recreated using the Neighbor-Joining method³¹, as shown in the optimal tree. The robustness of the branching pattern was assessed using bootstrap analysis, with the percentage of replicate trees supporting the taxon grouping shown beneath each branch⁵. The tree was drawn to show the proportionate magnitude of the evolutionary distances, which were calculated using the Kimura 2-parameter method³⁷ and were expressed in terms of the number of base substitutions per site. A gamma distribution with a shape parameter of one was used to model the variation in the rate of evolution

across sites. 15 nucleotide sequences with codon positions 1st+2nd+3rd+Noncoding were used in this study, and all ambiguous positions were removed using pairwise deletion. The final dataset comprised 1378 positions, and the evolutionary analyses were conducted using MEGA1138.

Strain Details:

Strain I: **KP07**

Phylogenetic Tree:

Figure 1. The phylogenetic tree constructed for the bacteria isolated from local Prawn sp. (*Fenneropenaeus indicus*), based on the partial sequences of the 16S rRNA gene using the neighbour-joining method.

Pigment Extraction:

The pigment-producing isolates were cultured for four days at room temperature in a shaker incubator in a sterile nutrient broth. The cultivated biomass was dissolved in 25 mL of 100% methanol and thoroughly mixed by vortexing to start the pigment extraction procedure. The extracted pigment was determined to be intracellular because no pigment was extracted from the centrifuged broth and it was found to be insoluble. To remove the intracellular pigment, the broth culture was spun at 7800 rpm for 10 minutes at 4 °C. After spotting the yellow pigment in the pellet, the supernatant was discarded. 100% methanol was added to the pellet to make it soluble, and it was vortexed for 30 minutes at room temperature before being heated in a water bath at 65°C until the colour disappeared from the pellet and was dissolved in the methanol solvent. The mixture was centrifuged for 15 minutes at 4°C at 7800 rpm, and absorbance was measured across a range of wavelengths using a spectrophotometer³⁴.

Antibacterial Activity:

The extracted pigment was put to the test against five pathogenic bacteria that are known to have a significant negative impact on health²² using the agar well diffusion method. *Bacillus subtilis* and *Staphylococcus aureus*, both gram-positive bacteria, were employed. *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*, *Proteus vulgaris*, and *Klebsiella pneumoniae* were the three Gram-negative pathogens used. Based on the gram nature of the bacterium, streptomycin and penicillin, in a 1:100 dilution, were used as a positive control. The preparation and solidification of nutrient agar plates were done. The test bacteria were grown in nutrient broth and incubated for 24 hours at 37°C. At 520 nm, the optical density of the culture that was being incubated in nutrient broth was measured. Onto the solidified nutrient agar plate, 100ul of the culture was swabbed. A sterile cork-borer was used to create 6 mm diameter wells in the agar plates. The dilutions of the extracted pigment were made ranging from 1:1 till 1:5 with methanol as diluent with the corresponding concentrations of 0.5, 0.33, 0.25, 0.2

and 0.16 v/v respectively. Each plate corresponding to the designated bacterium received a 50ul sample in each of the well per dilution of the extracted test substance. 50ul of the corresponding antibiotic was used as a positive control and 50ul of methanol was used as the negative control. The samples were incubated for 24 hours at 37°C. The diameter of the inhibition zone was measured after incubation. The antimicrobial activity was measured in millimeters by the size of the zone of growth inhibition around the wells². For each pathogenic bacterium, the experiment was performed in triplicates, and the results were reported as the mean standard deviation¹⁵.

Antioxidant Activity of Extracted Pigment:

The DPPH radical scavenging method, which measures the pigment's capacity to neutralize the stable free radical DPPH (2,2-diphenyl-1-picrylhydrazyl) through electron transfer, was used to assess the antioxidant activity of the pigment. The assay involves mixing DPPH solution with the pigment solution and then using a spectrophotometer to measure the change in DPPH absorbance at 517 nm. The antioxidant activity of the pigment is inversely correlated with the degree of DPPH decolorization. 0.5 mL of the extracted pigment in concentrations of 200, 160, 120, 80, and 40 mg/ml each were combined with a DPPH methanol solution to test a sample's antioxidant activity against DPPH radicals. The standard ascorbic acid concentrations (200, 160, 120, 80, and 40 mg/ml) were also prepared. The mixture was then kept at room temperature in a dark place for 24 hours⁴¹. Methanol was used as blank, and DPPH-methanol solution was used as control¹³. The capacity of DPPH radical scavenging for ascorbic acid and the pigment was calculated from the following equation: DPPH Radical Scavenging Activity (%) = $[1 - (\text{Absorbance of Sample} / \text{Absorbance of Control})] \times 100$, where A_t is the absorbance of the sample and A_o is the absorbance of the control. By comparing the absorbance of the sample (A_t) to the absorbance of the control, the equation calculates the DPPH radical scavenging efficiency as a percentage⁷. The higher the DPPH radical scavenging efficiency, the greater the ability of the sample to scavenge DPPH radicals. The antioxidant activity of selected isolates was compared using an ascorbic acid standard graph plotted in the range of 40–200 mg/ml.

Pigment Characterization:

The extracted pigment was analyzed using a gas chromatography mass spectrometer fitted with a JSW DB-1 silica capillary column (30m X 0.25 mm X 0.25um)²⁶. The temperature of the GC oven was first set at 50 °C (held for 4 minutes), then increased to 290 °C at a rate of 8 °C/min (10 minutes hold). With an electron energy of 70 eV, the mass spectrometer was in positive ion mode. The GC-MS Inlet port temperature was 290°C, the injection temperature was 250°C, and the ion source temperature was 230 °C. The carrier gas had a flow rate of 1.5 mL/min, a split ratio of 10:1, and was made up of 99.99% pure helium. The injection volume was 1.5 ml, and the injection mode was manual¹⁹. The components of the pigment were identified by comparing their retention times and mass spectra to the NIST mass spectral library⁴³.

RESULT AND DISCUSSION

Prawns are crucial to the health of the ocean because they control the nutrient cycle. They may be used in biomedical research, monitoring of aquatic ecosystems, and the production of cosmetics and medications⁹. They can also be used to lubricate surgical instruments and treat skin conditions in medicine. Given the paucity of information on pigments from bacteria isolated from prawns, studying the antibacterial and antioxidant properties of an Indian prawn pigment is a novel and important research topic. This research has the potential to fill the knowledge gap and provide valuable insights into potential applications in fields such as food science, medicine, and pharmaceuticals. In the past, red colored pigment astaxanthin was isolated from Shrimp using proteolytic digestion¹⁷, Lactic Fermentation and Enzymatic Hydrolysis¹.

Micrococcus luteus NCTC 2665(T) isolated from Indian prawns, was used to extract the pigment octadecanoic acid, and its antioxidant and antibacterial properties were investigated. Using GC-MS, the pigment was recognized as octadecanoic acid, also known as stearic acid. Nine L-asparaginase producing pigmented bacterial isolates were found in Indian prawn sample. Out of nine isolates KP07 displayed the strongest pigmentation and highest L-asparaginase producing ability when streaked on various media containing nalidixic acid (**L-asparaginase production is not the part of this article**). The 16S rRNA gene was used to identify the pigment-producing bacterial isolate, and the Neighbor-Joining method was used to reconstruct the phylogenetic tree. The isolate was identical to *Micrococcus luteus* NCTC 2665(T) by 99.72%. Pairwise similarities ranged from 100 to 99 percent, according to the comparative 16S rRNA gene-based phylogenetic

analysis. It can be assumed that this could be a different genus of the *Micrococcus* based on the results of the phylogenetic tree using the 1,484 bp sequence of the 16S rRNA gene and pairwise similarity results using the GenBank database. The analysis used a 1,484 bp sequence of the 16S rRNA gene, and the data indicates that 1253 sites were conserved while 122 sites were variable, and 69 sites were parsimony informative. The substitution model used in the analysis was Tajima-Nei, and the gap or missing data treatment was pairwise deletion. The phylogenetic tree was constructed with 1000 bootstrap replications, the observation suggests that strain KP07 is a novel species in the genus *Micrococcus*¹⁶. Similar studies have shown that yellow-orange pigmented *Sphingomonas japonica* was isolated from the marine crustacean *Paralithodes camtschatica*³⁰ and yellow pigmented *Vibrio owensii* sp. was isolated from cultured crustaceans⁴.

Gram-positive *Micrococcus luteus* is a member of the Micrococcaceae family of bacteria. It is an opportunistic pathogen with a coccus shape that sickens people with weakened immune systems. While making the discovery of lysozyme, Sir Alexander Fleming first identified the bacterium. *M. luteus* is a non-motile, yellow-pigmented bacterium that is frequently found in soil, dust, water, and air as well as on mammal skin. This saprophytic bacterium exhibits catalase and urease positivity and is bacitracin³³ susceptible.

The DPPH assay and agar well diffusion were used to examine the pigments' antioxidant and antibacterial properties. Similar research was done on the antibacterial properties of marine bacteria from barnacles (*Austrocochlea concamerata*)⁴² and spiny lobster (*Panulirus ornatus*)²⁴ as well as the antibacterial activity of *Allium sativum* against *Vibrio herveyi*³⁹ and *Vibrio parahaemolyticus*⁴⁰, which were isolated from *Fenneropenaeus indicus*. The pigment was tested using agar well diffusion against five pathogenic bacteria and proved to be highly toxic to the KP07 bacterial strain (*Micrococcus luteus* NCTC 2665(T)).

Figure 2. Bar graph of antibacterial activity of pigment extract.

It is apparent from the bar graph in figure 2 that the antibacterial activity of the sample varies according to the bacterial strains examined. The sample's antibacterial activity against *S. aureus* was at its peak at a 1:4 dilution, with an average zone of inhibition of 18.0 ± 0.2 mm. When compared to the negative control methanol, *P. vulgaris* and *B. subtilis* both demonstrated a significant sensitivity to the sample, with average zone sizes of 15.0 ± 0.2 mm and 14.6 ± 0.2 mm, respectively, at a 1:5 dilution. The pigment has significant antibacterial activity against *S. aureus*, according to the results of the agar well diffusion method, which may have significant implications for its potential use as a therapeutic agent.

Figure 3. Bar graph of % DPPH Radical Scavenging Activity between various concentrations of pigment and ascorbic acid.

From figure 3, at a concentration of 40 ug/ml, from the bar graph, we can infer that the pigment has maximum Radical Scavenging Activity determined by DPPH assay.

An analysis of Gas Chromatography-Mass Spectrometry was carried out to determine the pigment's identity which was found to be Octadecanoic Acid.

Figure 4. GC-MS analysis of extracted pigment.

The isolate was cultured, the intracellular pigment was extracted, and it was examined using a spectrophotometer for absorbance testing and GC-MS analysis. Octadecanoic acid was the main constituent of the pigment sample, according to the GC-MS analysis, with the highest peak accounting for 36.53% of the entire composition. Octadecanoic acid also has the second-highest peak, indicating that the sample contained abundance of this substance. The presence of (E) 5-Eicosene is also important since it makes up 23.92% of the composition. This substance, an unsaturated hydrocarbon, might help determine the pigment's color or other characteristics. Despite being relatively low at 3.89%, the peak corresponding to n-Octadecanol may still be

significant. This compound is a fatty alcohol and may have some surfactant or emulsifying properties. Gas Chromatography-Mass Spectrometry (GC-MS) has been utilized to analyze pigments extracted from marine crustaceans, such as astaxanthin³⁶ and carotenoids²¹. A typical saturated fatty acid with many industrial and commercial uses is octadecanoic acid, also referred to as stearic acid²⁷. It has a chain length of 18 carbons and is a saturated fatty acid. It is present in many oils made from both plants and animals. In addition to candles and lubricants, it is frequently used in the manufacturing of soaps, cosmetics, and other personal care products⁴⁶. It serves a crucial function in the phospholipids that make up cell membranes. Its chemical structure is C₁₈H₃₆O₂. With a melting point of 69–70°C, octadecanoic acid is a white, waxy solid characterized by high melting point and insolubility in water. It is also used in a variety of food products, including chocolate, pastries, and confectionery. It is also used in the manufacture of nonstick cooking surfaces as a release agent. It is used as an emulsifying agent, thickener, and opacifying agent in lotions, creams, and soaps in the personal care and cosmetic industries. It is used as a hardening agent in the manufacture of candles, increasing the melting point and rigidity of the candle and making it less likely to melt or bend at high temperatures. It is used as a lubricant in the pharmaceutical industry, allowing tablets to be produced with less sticking to the machinery during the manufacturing process. It also has biofuel potential because it can be converted into biodiesel, a renewable, clean-burning alternative to diesel fuel.

CONCLUSION

In conclusion, the pigment octadecanoic acid was extracted from the bacterial strain (*Micrococcus luteus* NCTC 2665(T)) which was isolated from Indian prawn *Fenneropenaeus indicus* and its antibacterial and antioxidant properties were studied. Using GC-MS, the pigment was recognized as octadecanoic acid, also known as stearic acid. There haven't been any prior studies on the extraction and identification of this particular pigment from this prawn species, so the process of extracting the pigment from the prawn species, its identification using GC-MS, and its subsequent antibacterial and antioxidant analysis are novel. Therefore, this research may offer helpful information about the pigment's chemical makeup and potential applications. Future prospects for this study include further investigations into the potential applications of the extracted pigment from prawns, including its cytotoxicity study, purification of the pigment to increase its potency, and increasing the yield of the pigment. Overall, this study provides a strong foundation for future research in the field of natural pigment extraction, and there are many potential avenues for exploration that could yield potentially new discoveries and applications of bacterial sp. Isolated from prawns.

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